

Presentations dealt with a wide range of topics including Royal Society of Chemistry Resources for Teachers, Oide Supports for Chemistry teachers and the Apprenticeship Route to Laboratory Technician or Laboratory Analyst.

Table 1. Speakers and Workshop Facilitators

Speaker / Workshop Facilitator	Activity
Louise Hussein , RSC Ed. Community Ireland Region Invited Speaker	Resources to Support Chemistry Teachers
Sean Kelleher , Oide	Oide Supports for Chemistry Teachers
John O'Donoghue , Royal Society of Chemistry	Royal Society of Chemistry Resources for Teachers
Claire McDonnell , Technological University Dublin	The Apprenticeship Route to Laboratory Technician or Laboratory Analyst
Sarah Rawe , Technological University Dublin	WS1: Escape Room Type Puzzles on Core Chemistry Topics
John O'Donoghue , RSC & Trinity College Dublin	WS2: From CBAs to AACs: How to Write a Lab Report
Sean Kelleher and Declan Cronin , Oide	WS3: Modelling pH Titration Curves and Exploring Challenges in Weak Acid-Weak Base Systems
Ryan Gallagher , Lecturer in Science Education, UCC	WS4: Using Wireless Electronic Sensor Technology to Gather Primary Data in Experiments Relevant to the New Curriculum Specification in Chemistry
Susan Kelleher , Dublin City University, Invited Speaker	Applications of Chemistry – from Recycling Textile Waste to Studying Lunar Dust
Claire McDonnell , Technological University Dublin	Resources to Support Chemistry Teachers

The guest speakers were [Louise Glynn](#) (Fig. 1), teaching and learning lead teacher at an independent girls' school in South London, who shared her expertise on 'Resources to Support Chemistry Teachers (including the Science Capital teaching approach)' and [Susan Kelleher](#) (Fig. 2), Dublin City University who guided us through the many fascinating research projects she has been involved in when she spoke about 'Applications of Chemistry – from Recycling Textile Waste to Studying Lunar Dust'.

Figure 1. Louise Glynn's talk on resources to support chemistry teachers

Figure 2. Susan Kelleher's presentation on applications of chemistry

There were also exhibits from CJ Fallon, Lennox Educational, the Royal Society of Chemistry, Current Chemistry Investigators and the LOESS soil health education project.

Figure 3. Some of the event's exhibitors and sponsor stands

Further information on the event is available at the [conference website](#).

Acknowledgements

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We are also very grateful to our workshop facilitators and invited speakers and to the teachers and student teacher who gave up their Saturday to take part.

Previous Events in this Series

This is the 44th Chem Ed Ireland conference.

43rd Chem Ed Ireland: University College Cork; <https://ista.ie/chemed-2024/>

42nd Chem Ed Ireland: Trinity College Dublin; https://www.tcd.ie/news_events/events/event/chemed-ireland-2023.php